

README_file

Supplementary file 1 contains the sample (31 species of extant tetrapods) and the phylogeny (topology and divergence times; see main text for references) used to test the relationships between the response variables (RBC_{width} and RBC_{area}) and the explanatory variables (femoral vascular canal diameter and femoral cross-sectional area including the medullary cavity) using PGLS.

Supplementary file 2 contains data used to test the relationships between RBC_{width} and RBC_{area} and the explanatory variables femoral vascular canal diameter (computed as $Can_{harmean}$ and Can_{min}) and femoral cross-sectional area through PGLS.

Supplementary file 3 contains data used to construct the thermophysiology inference model (to infer the probability of being endothermic) constructed using femoral vascular canal diameter ($Can_{harmean}$ and Can_{min}) and femoral cross-sectional area as explanatory variables using PLR.